

* Evelina Mezalina Graur
 Faculty of Letters and Communication Sciences,
 University Ștefan cel Mare of Suceava,
 Universităţii Street 13, 720229 Suceava, Romania
 e-mail: evelina.graur@usv.ro

GOING DOWN THE RABBIT HOLE OF WORDSMITHERY

Abstract

The present article revisits two basic linguistic models and links them to the *onomasiological model of word formation*. The first section of the articles focusses on the main tenets of Štekauer’s model of research into English word-formation and points to some of its advantages. In the second part of the article, we absolutize the principle of ‘linguistic need’ in an attempt to organize an eclectic collection of linguistic facts, attitudes and new coinages.

Keywords: word, naming unit, need, social tool

1. The need for words: from basic linguistic models to new theories of word formation

Brümmer (1981) reminds us that there are two major roads that diverge in the ‘wordy woods’. To put it differently, there are two major linguistic models explaining the relationship between words, things and concepts. The first one is represented by the *names model*, which invites us to consider words as signs referring to the structural divisions of reality represented in concepts. The second one is the *tools model*, which proposes us to regard words as instruments to be employed in performing various speech acts in relation to things. The central tenets of the two models are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Words, things and concepts in two major linguistic models (Brümmer, 1981: 55)

<i>The Names Model</i>	<i>The Tools Model</i>
<i>Concepts:</i> Mental representations corresponding to the structural divisions in reality. According to <i>realism</i> these divisions are inherent in reality. According to conceptualism these divisions are applied by us when perceiving reality.	<i>Concepts:</i> Forms of thought or mental skills which we usually exercise verbally. A great variety, not to be limited to classification skills which we exercise when dividing reality into classes.
<i>Words:</i> Names for concepts and hence also for the structural divisions of reality to which our concepts correspond.	<i>Words:</i> Tools which we use to exercise a large variety of conceptual skills.
<i>Reality:</i> That of which the structural divisions are reflected in our concepts. Words (as names for concepts) can be used to refer to these structural divisions or to classify things according to these divisions.	<i>Reality:</i> The factual context within which we exercise our conceptual skills and which is partly constitutive for the exercise of these conceptual skills.
<i>The Meaning of a Word:</i> the concepts (or thing or class of things) for which that word stands, or to which it refers.	<i>The Meaning of a Word:</i> the conceptual skills exercised with that word in the speech acts performed with sentences containing the word.

* Dr. Evelina Mezalina Graur is Senior Lecturer in English at the Department of Foreign Studies, Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava, where she teaches English lexicology, terminology, ESP, media discourse and communication classes. Her research is mainly focused on language use in social and cultural contexts. Her latest articles entitled “The Multimodal Existence of Résumés” (2022) and “Restaurant Menus: A McLuhanesque Perspective” (2021) have been published in *ANADISS* and *Romanian Journal of Artistic Creativity*, respectively.

The two models are obviously dichotomous because the *names model* places the lexical item at the level of the *language system* (or *langue*) and the *tools model* places it at the level of *language use* (or *parole*). Consequently, scholars always embrace the view that best supports their cause. In this respect, Pavol Štekauer’s onomasiological model of word formation is rooted in the *names model* because he sets his point of departure in extra-linguistic reality, more precisely in the naming needs of a speech community, and seeks to obtain the lexemic form through conceptual reflection of extra-linguistic reality and semantic analysis. As he explains in a note, his constant preference for and usage of the term *naming unit* (instead of *word*, *lexeme* or *lexical item*) matches the determination of any coiner to get a single form for a single meaning: “[...] because from the perspective of newly formed complex words to refer to newly perceived objects of reality it really is a case of consciously ‘naming’ the object rather than subconsciously referring to it” (Štekauer, 2005: 265).

According to the Slovakian scholar, any act of coining a *naming unit* presupposes the following sequence of levels: 1. Extra-linguistic reality. 2. Speech community. 3. Conceptual level. 4. Semantic level. 5. Onomasiological level. 6. Onomatological level. 7. Phonological level.

The model was developed as a reaction to some major deficiencies identified in previous approaches: 1. a prevailing linguistic formalism in which the semantic component of word formation is neglected and in which the morpheme is not always regarded as an indestructible *unit of form and meaning*; 2. discussions and interpretations focusing on purely linguistic aspects and neglecting extra-linguistic reality and speech communities; 3. the assignment of two incompatible constituent structures to the same expression (i.e. bracketing paradoxes); 4. no sharp boundaries between compounding and affixal derivation. The main principles governing Štekauer’s model are collected in Table 2.

Table 2. Major tenets of Pavol Štekauer’s onomasiological model of English word formation

Tenet 1	The participatory role of language users in the process of giving names to objects. The close interconnection between extra-linguistic reality and a speech community predetermines all the subsequent steps in coining a naming unit.
Tenet 2	The naming act/ process is not a purely linguistic act, but also a cognitive process relying on the intellectual capacity of those who identify a particular linguistic need.
Tenet 3	There is a close interconnection between linguistic and extralinguistic phenomena.
Tenet 4	The Word-Formation Component is an independent component of linguistic description, interconnected with the Lexical Component and separated from the Syntactical Component.
Tenet 5	The Lexical Component is the storage place of all naming units of a language, including monemes (e.g. <i>receive</i> , <i>cranberry</i> , <i>retain</i>), immediate regular and predictable outputs of productive Word Formation Rules, lexicalized items, all affixes (including their combinability specifications, usage restrictions and phonological properties).
Tenet 6	The sign-nature of naming units. Naming units are <i>bilateral signs</i> , including the meaning and the form. Naming units such as <i>receive</i> , <i>cranberry</i> or <i>retain</i> are treated as monemes.
Tenet 7	No naming units are generated from units smaller than the morpheme and all productively coined naming units are formed by application of the principle Form-to-Seme Assignment

Since Štekauer’s approach is deeply rooted in the interconnectedness between word formation and the conceptual level, the whole process of coining a word starts with unveiling the complex ‘knowledge structure’ of the object to be labelled via a logical spectrum (logical predicates and conceptual categories such as SUBSTANCE, ACTION, QUALITY and CONCOMITANT CIRCUMSTANCE.). To follow Štekauer’s example (2005: 46-47), if we need to coin a naming unit denoting ‘a person whose job is to drive a vehicle designed to transport goods’, the conceptual analysis gets the following configuration:

It is SUBSTANCE₁.
 SUBSTANCE₁ is Human.
 The Human performs ACTION.
 ACTION is the Human’s Profession.
 ACTION concerns SUBSTANCE₂.
 SUBSTANCE₂ is a class of Vehicles.

The Vehicles are designed for Transporting goods.
Etc.

The next step involves mapping the individual logical predicates of the conceptual level onto the semantic level of the expected linguistic sign by means of *semes* (i.e. *general semes*, capable of covering any object in extra-linguistic reality, namely SUBSTANCE, ACTION, QUALITY, and CIRCUMSTANCE, *classification semes*, *identification semes*, *prototypical semes* and *idiosyncratic semes*). Our configuration might look as follows:

SUBSTANCE
[+MATERIAL] [+ANIMATE] [+HUMAN] [+ADULT] [+AGENT]
[+PROFESSION]
[+MATERIAL] [-ANIMATE] [+VEHICLE]
[+TRANSPORTATION] [+OBJECT OF OPERATION], etc

The onomasiological level comprises two elements: the *onomasiological base* (always simple), and the *onomasiological mark* (can be both simple and complex). In the process of naming, we may decide that the polar members of the onomasiological structure, namely the *base* and the *mark*, become SUBSTANCE₁ and SUBSTANCE₂, respectively. Since the onomasiological structure reflects the relations between logico-semantic categories (such as Agent, Patient, Logical Object, Instrument, Time, Action, Process, etc.), we need to decide on an appropriate structural solution, for instance one “in which the onomasiological base stands for Agent (the class of Humans performing the Action as their Profession) of Action (the determined constituent of the onomasiological mark) aimed at its Object, i.e., the class of Vehicles (the determining constituent of the onomasiological mark): [(Logical) Object ← Action – Agent]” (Štekauer, 2005: 50).

The next level is the onomatological level, where naming units stored in the Lexicon are assigned to the individual members of the onomasiological structure, following the *Form-to-Seme-Assignment Principle*. There are several options at this level: the Agent may be expressed by word-formation bases such as *man* or by affixes such as *-er*, *-ist*, *-ant*, or *-ian*. Action can be expressed by word-formation bases of naming units such as *drive*, *operate*, *steer* or *pilot*. The Object can be represented by *truck*, *lorry* or even other word-formation base, the meaning of which is Vehicle. Here is a possible configuration:

Object – Action – Agent
truck *drive* *-er*

At the phonological level, the naming unit is assigned its corresponding stress pattern: '*truck*, *driver* (['] for primary stress and [,] for secondary stress).

One major advantage of this model is that it can accommodate naming units that are problematic in theories in which word formation rules operate only with attested words. Forms such as *sleeved*, *headed* or *hearted* have no independent status as lexical items, and yet they are present in compounds such as *shirt-sleeved*, *pig-headed* and *lion-hearted*. The bypassing of the unattested forms can be explained by applying the onomasiological principles.

The coinage of *lion-hearted* is explainable through conceptual analysis. ‘To be very courageous’ is a QUALITY, which resembles the general behaviour [(brave) heart] of a lion. The set of semes selected for the linguistic sign comprise [+QUALITY], [+BEHAVIOUR], [+COURAGE] and [+PATTERN]. The mark and the base of the onomasiological structure will be:

SUBSTANCE - QUALITY

Following the application of the Form-to-Seme Assignment Principle, the onomatological structure will have the following configuration:

The onomasiological approach also solves the problem of syntactically conditioned generation of naming units. In generative grammar a verbal compound such as *peace-thinker* is syntactically rejected (i.e. *to think peace) and considered an impossible formation. In fact, its onomasiological structure (Štekauer, 1998: 92) is the same with that of other naming units such as *dream-seller*, *promise-breaker* or *trouble-shooter*:

ACT	-	SUBSTANCE
Object [=state]	<-	Act Agent

Within this approach, the role of word-formation is to *denominate* while the role of syntax is to *describe*. Never mixing *langue* with *parole*, Štekauer rejects the idea of the transformational origin of naming units from sentence structures and considers that the semantic parallelism residing in “what is named by naming units is described by sentences” (1998: 44) is an indicator of *functional* difference:

It is true that any object, action, phenomenon, or circumstance can be described instead of naming it, and that the description precedes the act of naming. This is one side of the problem. But there is another side which pertains to the relation between such a description and the act of naming. Clearly, the discussed relation is a meaning relation: what is described, i.e. the conceptual meaning, is to be compressed within a single naming unit. The form plays its role in terms of speech economy. The language would be rather cumbersome if we confined ourselves to the existing list of naming units, using them for describing all new facts of the extra-linguistic reality. There is no other reason to postulate a connection between a description (syntactic construction) and a naming unit. The mechanisms of the formation of naming unit, and the mechanisms of their functioning are completely different from those of syntactic descriptions. The only relation is that of the parallel meaning. In other words, syntactic description functions as a semantic point of departure for the act of naming, although not always as a comprehensive semantic starting point. A more complex and a more suitable source is a definition, or, as in our approach, the capturing of the “object” to be denominated by means of a logical spectrum, a set of noems, logical predicates, identifying the fundamental properties of the respective object. (Štekauer, 1998: 40)

2. Naming demands and new coinages

The onomasiological model dismisses the dichotomy *possible word/impossible word* because its prerequisite is the very existence of a *speech community* and a particular speech-community demand, “be it the demand of a single member of the speech-community, or be it a single-act, unrepeated demand” (Štekauer. 1998: 92). In this respect, the scholar sees no linguistic impediment to accept *peace-thinker* as an *actual* naming unit “if a speech community finds it necessary to coin a naming unit standing for a person who habitually, frequently, or even professionally, thinks of peace”. At the same time, one cannot exclude the possibility for ad-hoc/nonce formations to be lexicalized. In fact, while investigating the degree of meaning predictability in word-formation, Štekauer (2005) discovered that the reading proposed by one of his informants for the naming unit *apple juice seat* (i.e., ‘a seat for drinking apple juice in a restaurant, bar, etc’) was the generalized version of Downing’s ‘deictic’ interpretation (i.e. ‘seat in front of which a glass of apple juice [is] placed’ (1977: 818, apud Štekauer 2005: 131).

In his 2016 book, IEEE *Spectrum*’s former language columnist Paul McFedries reiterates the idea that it is technology and its communities that have initiated and driven language evolution. *Merriam Websters Dictionary* pinpoints the first-known use of the term *cloud computing* to 1996. McFedries also mentioned this word in his 2008 column in a context which clearly suggests that the naming unit was meant to designate a new solution in the technological paradigm of network-based computing: “In fact, we’re on the verge of **cloud computing**, in which not just our data but even our

software resides within the cloud” (our underlining, IEED *Spectrum*, August 2008, p. 16). The identity of the coiner of *cloud computing* was not indifferent to MIT *Technology Review*, which managed to find and attest through company documents and pictures of the handwritten term on a business plan that *cloud computing* was coined within a now-defunct company called NetCentric. In spite of all controversies and conflicting evidence presented in the article written by Regalado (2011), what matters is that a consuming professional need identified at the intersection of marketing and computing was eventually fulfilled.

A rather more recent example of an openly declared need for words comes from a website called *The Bureau of Linguistical Reality*, which was created in 2014 by artists Alicia Escott and Heidi Quante. Judging by its mission statement (<https://bureauoflinguisticalreality.com/mission-statement/>), we might be led to believe that the phenomenon that John McWhorter (2016) describes as a ‘personal pull on words’ meanings’ (i.e. when some words stop being the name of a person, place, thing action or trait and become an expression of personal feeling, namely *modal pragmatic markers*) is counterbalanced by a shortage of naming units in areas such as people’s emotions and experiences in our planetary habitat influenced by climate changes and unprecedented events. Some words and phrases in the Bureau’s mission statement (i.e. a “new vocabulary for the Anthropocene”, “to help fill the linguistical void in our rapidly changing world”) impart some urgency to the naming task. It is worth noticing that the process of *co-creating* words does not imply the usage of only one language. In fact, most coinages are non-English words and even pluri-language words, and they all reflect people’s very personal experiences, fears or concerns about their lives in today’s world (e.g. *nonapaura*, Italian, for ‘conflicting fears and hopes of becoming a grandparent amid climate change’, from *nona* (grandmother) and *paura* (fear); *mienterra*, Spanish, for ‘a false sense of solid ground under our feet’, from *miente* (he/she lies) and *tierra* (land); *chuco* ☞ *sol*, a mixture of ElSalvadorian slang, Korean and Spanish meaning ‘dirty-wow-sun’ to refer to the polluted Los Angeles sunset). With no chances of being institutionalized and lexicalized in (any) one language, these nonce words are likely to fade away or show sporadic repetitive usage and endurance in very tight circles. Nevertheless, the online medium in which these words are circulated will probably contribute to their ‘digital endurance and usage’ and will increase their chances of manifesting themselves as ‘social tools’ in discussions, clarifications, debates and attempts at changing or reshaping cultural paradigms. The latest experiments on the acquisition of abstract concepts conducted by Borghi et al (2019) already confirm important tenets of the Words as Social Tools (WAT) Theory: the acquisition of abstract concepts relies more on social and linguistic inputs; abstract concepts are more affected by differences between spoken languages; abstract concepts tend to activate more the oral motor system.

The English language scholar David Crystal was also in need of a word to refer to the “cessation of anxiety when our luggage eventually emerges from the black hole of an airport carousel (2006: 26).” He coined the word *debagonization* to illustrate that one can rely on already existing linguistic building blocks for the creation of a new word and then use it to exchange travel opinions and experiences. The word has not made it yet in English dictionaries. This does not necessarily mean that the coinage has no relevance for language users, but perhaps the *perception of the intended meaning* is still too weak even among English language users who travel by plane and encounter the same problem as the famous linguist.

3. Conclusive remarks

Among the editorial decisions of most online dictionaries is the publication of a word risen to stardom for a day. Sometimes the word of the day is not some long-forgotten formal or informal lexical item or loanword that steps into the spotlight, but a new coinage that is expected to fill in a gap and designate a new concept. For instance, the word *deepfake*, whose first *known* use goes back to 2018, was selected by *Merriam Webster Dictionary* for May 8th 2023: “an image or recording that has been convincingly altered and manipulated to misrepresent someone as doing or saying something that was not actually done or said.” (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/deepfake>) As the graph in Figure 1 illustrates, it was around 2015 when this new unit of form and meaning started to gain some currency in major publications and eventually lexicographers decided to grant its dictionary inclusion.

Figure 1. The birth of *deepfake* recorded in Google Ngram

The roots of our fascination and obsession with words “lie deep in the history of human race” (Crystal, 2006: 4). Moreover, it seems there is compelling evidence in our own vocabulary and in some of our actions or doings that we are destined to live in a universe of words:

We even have names for those who are aware that they live in this universe and who have become mildly or seriously obsessed by it. We call them wordsmiths, word-buffs, wordaholics. We feed their obsession by publishing books of wordgames, putting wordpuzzles in newspapers, playing wordgames on radio or television, and setting up word websites. There are now thousands of places on the Internet where they can indulge themselves. World Wide Web was a misnomer. It should have been Word Wide Web. (Crystal, 2006: 3).

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